

Numerical Simulation of Jigs and Tools for CFRP-parts

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SUMMARY

Simulation is of main interest for a lean development chain inside design of jigs and tools for CFRP-parts manufacturing. Therefore different simulation tools can be used for most effective development of needed toolings. Due to their field of application the simulation of toolings can vary from FEM-simulation, autoclave- or thermal-simulation, fluid-dynamic-simulation and others. Some off their applications are described in the following article.

Keywords: Autoclave-simulation, FEM-Simulation, Fluid-dynamic simulation

FEM-SIMULATION OF A RTM-TOOLING

Composites gain an increasing importance in modern aviation industry. Responding to this development, also the respective jigs and tools have to be developed further since processing composites poses new requirements towards the tools as there is a significant interdependence between the characteristics of the tool and the achievable quality of the part. Due to the higher complexity of the parts, this interrelation can no longer be predicted based on experience but has to be precisely evaluated.

Premium AEROTEC's Department of Production Systems reacts to this challenge by means of simulation such as the determination of the deflection of an RTM-tool caused by resin-pressure. As an object of investigation a tool for a test-frame, which is shown in Figure 1 with its dimensions, was chosen.

The tool mainly consists of a base-plate and a lid being compressed by bolts to simulate the configuration during manufacture in a furnace environment. As the bolts tie down the lid, the slant of the con-tact-surface between the latter and the cores cause a compression of the cores resulting in a compression of the web in order to ensured the desired fibre-volume-content. The seals and the resin-ports function as auxiliary elements.

Figure 1: Object of investigation

The boundary conditions and influences which are taken into consideration in this study are enlisted in the following:

- Increase in temperature from 20 to 180 °C
- Difference in pressure 7 bar
- Influence of the tool-components
- Contact conditions
- Compression of seals
- Resulting lid force
- Weight
- Cure in oven or under heated press

It becomes obvious, that the selection of the appropriate boundary conditions, e.g. the contact definition between the base-plate and the lid, has a decisive influence on the result. The determined deformation would cause the part to be outside the specified geometry

The areas where and the way how the loads are applied are pointed out in Fig. 2. It is assumed further, that the tool is processed in a furnace and there is no limitation of the deflection by a heated press.

Figure 2: Forces applied to the FE-model

The resin-pressure impacts on all surfaces encompassed by the inner seal whereas the bolt-forces act on the edges of the bolt-holes in the lid.

Fig. 3 shows the results of the numerical calculation of the deflection caused by the internal resin-pressure. It becomes obvious, that the formulation of the contact definition between the base-plate and the lid has a decisive influence on the deflected shape.

Figure 3: Deformation of RTM-tool caused by resin-pressure in dependence of boundary conditions

AUTOCLAVE-SIMULATION

One further field of simulation within in the scope of Jigs and Tools comprises the study of the flow- and temperature-field in an autoclave with Computational Fluid Dynamics. This is of special interest with regard to the curing-process of shell-parts on layup-tools, where the interaction of both, the de-sign of the autoclave as well as the design of the tool, has an influence on the warming of the part. For example, the design of the tool depends on the basic concept of the autoclave whether the flow is horizontal or vertical. Because of reasons of quality, a temperature-distribution as even as possible in the curing part is desired.

A schematic of the thermal and fluidic conditions in an autoclave with horizontal flow concept is presented in Fig. 4. Nitrogen, as a flow-medium, is circulated by a fan located at the far end of the auto-clave. Before flowing through the circumferential duct, the medium is brought to temperature in the heat-exchanger. The spherical shape of the lid directs the flow into the working-chamber of the auto-clave where the hot gas passes through the tool to start the circle again at the heat-exchanger. The cooling-section of the latter can be activated realize a specific cooling-rate if required.

Figure 4: Thermal and fluidic conditions in an autoclave

Substantial issue of the simulation is an evaluation of the design of the understructure at a very early stage to ensure a sufficient flow-rate and resulting in an even heat-distribution. The later the need for change is discovered, the more cost-intensive it becomes.

In addition, simulation in this field helps to plan the manufacturing process. Stacking more than one tool in an autoclave during one cycle facilitates a better exploitation of manufacturing capacities but has to be evaluated in terms of heat- and flow-conditions.

Figure 5: Longitudinal flow-field in an autoclave with a lay-up tool

An example result acquired with Computational Fluid Dynamics is presented in Fig. 5. The plot shows the velocity-distribution in longitudinal direction and especially points out eddy water regions near the lid implying that the tool should not be placed too close to these areas during the process.

It has been shown, that numerical simulation of the characteristics of tools particularly during the curing process of CFRP-parts can help to avoid part-failure if the expertise is fed back into the tool-design.

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